
VOCABULARY COMPOSITION OF MODERN ENGLISH

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Abstract: The vocabulary of a language is in a state of continuous change. This mobility and variability are due to the fact that language, and primarily its vocabulary, is directly related to both production and any other social activity of people. This article explores a range of vocabulary composition of modern English as a product of its development over a number of eras. In order for a language to fully fulfill its main function - the function of the most important means of communication - its vocabulary must quickly respond to changes occurring in all spheres of people's lives and activities: in production, in science, in worldview, in socio-economic relations, and finally, in everyday life; — reflect and record these changes.

Key words: vocabulary composition, borrowing word, compound word, modern English, Old English, complex words, zoological names, botanical names, archaisms, complex adjectives, concept, archaization, common nouns.

Concepts that arise in the course of social development need for their realization in linguistic matter, in verbal embodiment. The complication of the forms of social existence, the development and deepening of the entire sum of human knowledge of the surrounding reality causes the emergence of more and more new words and the gradual displacement from linguistic use of those words that were associated with the past stage of social practice and ideology. Thus, the quantitative growth and qualitative changes in the vocabulary of a language are ultimately connected with the history of the people, the creator and speaker of this language.

Generally speaking, an analysis of English word production and word usage shows that the name of a thing, both at the time of its appearance in the language and when it is used in linguistic communication, may not reflect any features or characteristics of the named object, much less its essence². This is clearly evidenced, first of all, by those numerous borrowed words that came into the English language as simple signs or labels of the facts of reality they denote. For example, borrowing word “prince” from the Old French language, the English people, of course, did not realize that this word represents a development of the Latin word “princeps” - “chief”, “head”, which, in turn, developed in Latin in based on the words “prim us” – “first”

² Е. М. Галкина-Федору к. «ость в ЯЗЫке с точки зрения марксистского языкознания, иностранные языки в школе», 1952, № 2.

and “capio” – “I take”. Thus, contained the attribute of the named person, as one who occupies the first (i.e., most important) position. In English, the word “prince” is simply the name of a certain person, a title, in no way in its material form reflecting the quality or any characteristics of this person or this title.

According to the terminology of Academician V.V. Vinogradov, a syntactical and morphological method of word formation, is a widespread phenomenon not only in English, but also in all other Indo-European languages.³ As is known, its essence lies in the fact that a new word is formed from two, less often three, existing full-valued bases, and, as a rule, the meaning of the newly formed whole becomes not identical to the sum of the meanings of its parts. Formation of English compounds is characterized by the absence of a connecting vowel between stems and a tendency to place stress on the first component of a compound word; sometimes, mainly in polysyllabic words, a secondary stress is allowed on the second component. Solving the problem of a compound word in modern English is complicated by the fact that in English the use of nouns in the general form is widely spread. Therefore, it can be difficult to find accurate and objective criteria for distinguishing between genuine complex words and stable attributive complexes. The articles of scientists such as O.S. Akhmanov and A.I. Smirnisky are useful in solving these linguistic problems.⁴

Compound word formation did not lose its importance as one of the leading word-formation processes at all stages of the development of the English language. It is true that many of the complex words that arose and were in use in ancient times, in the Middle Ages, and in the Renaissance, have long been outdated and can now only be found in ancient manuscripts or ancient books. But many of these ancient word formations have been preserved in modern linguistic use, and the extent of this heritage is so great that we are forced to limit ourselves here to only some condensed illustrations.⁵

From Old English, the vocabulary of modern English has inherited a number of complex nouns reflecting various types of concepts; for example, botanical names: oak-tree (Old English *ac-treow* “oak”), apple-tree (OE. *aeppel-treow* “apple tree”), plum-tree (OE. *plum-treow* “plum”), blackberry (OE. *blaeck erije* “black currant”), straw berry (OE. *strew berige* “strawberry”), brook mint (OE. *brocminste* “water mint”), stonecrop (OE. *stancropp* “sedum”), nightshade (OE. *nihtscada* “nightshade”), earthnut (OE. *eorphnutu* “groundnut”), hazelnut (OE. *haesel-hnutu* “nut”), linseed (OE. *linse:d* “flax seed”), peppercorn (OE. *piporcorn* “pepper”); zoological names: butterfly (OE. *buterfleoge* “butterfly”), earwig (OE. *earwicea*

³ В и н о г р а д о в В. В. . Об основном словарном фонде и его словообразующей роли в истории языка. «Известия АН СССР» вып. 3, 1951

⁴ А. И. Смирницкий. Так называемая конверсия и чередование звуков в английском языке. «Иностранные языки в школе», 1953, № 5, стр. 24.

⁵ О. Jespersen. A Modern English Grammar on Historical principles P. VI, G. Allen-Unwin, p. 135

“earwig”), goldfinch (OE. goldfinc “head”), greyhound (OE. jrighund “hound”), stud-horse (OE. stodhors “thoroughbred horse”), woodcock (OE. wuducocc “Waldsh nep”); names of family relationships: foster-child (OE. fostorcild “step-child”), godfather (OE. godfaeder “godfather”), godmother (OE. godmodor “godmother”), stepfather (OE. steopfaeder “foster father”), stepmother (OE. stepmodor “foster mother”); names of people by occupation and profession: cowherd (OE. cu-hierde “shepherd”), goldsmith (OE. goldsmij “goldsmith”), swineherd (OE. swlnehierde “swineherd”); names of the realities of work and life: bedclothes (OE. bedclajaas “bed linen”), coalpit (OE. colpytt “coal mine”), fire-shovel (OE. fyrscofl “scoop”), honeycomb (OE. hunig-camb “honey honeycomb”), homestead (OE. hamstede “homestead”), sunshade (OE. sunsceado “canopy”); names of phenomena and objects of the surrounding nature: eventide (OE. asfentld “evening”), quicksand (OE. cwecesand “quicksand”), moorland (OE. morland “heather field”), rainbow (OE. rejn-boga “rainbow”), waterfall (OE. waete efeall “waterfall”), etc.

Many of these models turned out to be very viable, continuing to stimulate the activity of these productive word-formation types at all stages of the historical development of the English language. For example, in the Middle English period there was a substitution of one of the components in the nouns beod-clati > tablecloth, deor-net > hunting-net, circetun > churchyard, both components in the words: campstede > battle-field, healswifia > necklace.

A number of complex adjectives have also come down to modern times from Old English, indicating the significant antiquity of some word-formation types within this part of speech. These are, for example, structural types: nominal stem + adjective, in particular, nominal stem + nominal adjective with the suffix -ede, in Middle English period: ice-cold (OE. Ts-calde “cold as ice”), iron-grey (OE. Iren -jre “iron-gray color”), half-bald (OE. healf-ballede “bald”), half-empty (OE. healf-emptig “half empty”), milk-white (OE. meolc-hwyte “milky white”), half-sour (OE. heal f-sur “half sour”), silver-hilted (OE. seolfor hiltede “with a silver handle”).

The vocabulary of the English language has retained a significantly larger number of compound words from the Middle English period than from Old English. This is partly explained by the fact that, although the Old English language was no less rich in complex words, many of them long ago became archaisms due to the archaization of the concepts they expressed, and partly by the fact that many Old English word formations were over time crowded out of the language by equivalent borrowed words. For example, bryne-adl “fever” - fever (OE. fefer; lat. febris), crst-waen “chariot” - chariot (French chariot), cu-sealf “interior fat” - suet (French suif), cynesetl “throne”, “capital” - throne (French throne), capital (French capitale), dream-craeft “muse” - music (French musique).

Among the compound nouns that came down from the Middle English period, the predominant type is the following: nominal stem + noun, for example, backbone, bagpipe, bearskin, beehive, blacksmith; bloodhound, grandfather, grandmother, harebell, nightgown, nightmare, pancake, penknife, pikestaff, ploughshare, roadstead, etc.

In the early New English period, the word-formation of the English language did not weaken at all, and a huge number of formations from this period still remain living elements of modern English vocabulary. Common nouns such as background, banknote, bedpost, billhook, birthright, book-keeper, bookseller, headline, keystone, lighthouse, lovelock, mouthpiece, quagmire, racehorse, part-owner, patchwork, pathway, pawnbroker, pincushion, playbill, rosebud, sawdust, etc., are the result of word creation in the 15th–17th centuries.

Conclusion: To summarize, word formation is a word-formation process that occurs in all eras of the existence of the English language, although, apparently, in the New English period it reduces its productivity as a result of the spread of stable noun combinations, from which, however, sometimes a complex word can be formed. In the vocabulary of modern English there are a large number of complex words that genetically go back to various periods in the history of the English language.

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